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Classification of Korean rice germplasm based on isozyme polymorphism

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Isozymes are important biochemical markers in genetic and plant breeding research. Isozyme polymorphism has provided useful information for classifying rice cultivars, thus enabling breeders to transfer desirable traits through hybridization within and between groups.

We analyzed traditional and modern rice cultivars from Korea using gel electrophoresis. Five isozyme loci (*Pgi1*, *Pgi2*, *Amp1*, *Amp2*, *Amp3*) were studied following the classification scheme of Glaszmann (1987). Zymograms were revealed following the staining procedure of Glaszmann et al (1988).

Of the 286 cultivars, 42 (14.7%) belonged to group 1 (indica types). This is the result of hybridization between indica and japonica types cultivated during 1976-80 as "Tongil type" in Korea. Most (242, or 84.6%) were classified as group VI (japonica types), which are currently heavily cultivated in Korea. Only two varieties were mixed. ■

Heritability and genetic correlation for component characters of yield sink capacity in rice

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Yield sink capacity (YSC), the maximum size of sink organs to be harvested per rice plant is a product of the number of grains plant⁻¹ (= number of panicles plant⁻¹ [NP] ×

Genetic correlation and realized heritability for traits related to yield sink capacity of rice.*

Trait ^b	YSC	NP	NG	NPB	NGPB	NSB	NGSB	GL	GW
NP	-0.449	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NG	0.748	-0.690	<u>0.200</u>	0.959	*0.281	*0.544	*0.130	-0.256	0.472
NPB	0.041	-0.467	0.342	<u>0.426</u>	*0.507	-0.108	-0.122	-0.155	0.515
NGPB	0.435	-0.347	0.687	0.504	<u>0.040</u>	-0.787	-0.187	0.136	0.470
NSB	0.636	-0.286	0.642	-0.495	0.168	<u>0.179</u>	*0.368	-0.103	*0.319
NGSB	0.720	-0.294	0.619	-0.454	0.231	0.917	<u>0.129</u>	0.124	-0.074
GL	0.246	0.030	-0.313	-0.319	-0.181	-0.050	0.113	<u>0.270</u>	*0.153
GW	0.267	-0.559	0.147	0.268	-0.178	-0.047	-0.022	0.052	<u>0.773</u>
RGP	-0.964	-0.046	-0.384	0.899	-0.180	-1.008	-1.184	-0.393	-0.028

*Above the diagonal (underlined): genetic correlation coefficients estimated from selection responses in F₂ and F₃ populations of Nakateshinsenbon/Hieri. * = Sign of coefficient could not be determined. The data for YSC, NP, and RGP were not available. Below the diagonal: genetic correlation coefficients estimated from variance and covariance components in recombinant inbreds of Koshihikari/Nakateshinsenbon. Diagonal (underlined): realized heritabilities estimated from selection responses in F₂ and F₃ populations of Nakateshinsenbon/Hieri. *See text for the meanings of the abbreviations.

number of grains panicle⁻¹ [NG]) multiplied by single grain weight. Grain ripening ability, measured as the ripened grain percentage (RGP), is generally superior for grains on primary branches compared with that for secondary branches. Therefore NG must be broken into components: number of primary branches panicle⁻¹ (NPB), number of grains on primary branches primary branch⁻¹ (NGPB), number of secondary branches primary branch⁻¹ (NSB), and number of grains on secondary branches secondary branch⁻¹ (NGSB).

We estimated genetic correlation (rg) for these YSC components using two experiments. In experiment I, genetic correlation was estimated from variance and covariance components in 49 recombinant inbred lines of Koshihikari/Nakateshinsenbon cultivated under four environments. In experiment II, rg was estimated from direct and correlated responses in selecting F₂ and F₃ populations (Falconer 1989) of Nakateshinsenbon/Hieri. Realized heritability was also estimated.

In experiment I, YSC was positively correlated with NG ($r = 0.748$), but not with grain length (GL) or grain width (GW). A high negative correlation was detected between YSC and RGP ($r = -0.964$), perhaps due to the negative correlations between RGP and NSB ($r = -1.008$) and RGP and NGSB ($r = -1.184$). In contrast, NPB was positively and tightly correlated with RGP ($r = 0.899$). In experiment II, NPB showed a high positive correlation with NG ($r = 0.959$) and the highest realized heritability among the NG components.

In addition, NPB was not positively correlated with NSB and NGSB in either experiment.

These results suggest a strategy for developing a promising panicle type that realizes both high NG and RGP that consists of increasing the NPB to provide numerous well-ripened grains and suppressing the NSB and/or NGSB to not overproduce unfilled grains.

Chau and Bhargava (1993) demonstrated that the large sink sizes of high-yielding indica cultivars were mainly due to high NPB and high NPB × NGPB. The genetic nature of NPB must be understood more precisely.

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Heading-time genes control photoperiod insensitivity of rice cultivar Norin 20

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Rice cultivars grown in Hokkaido, the highest latitude area (41-44 °N) in Japan, flower far earlier than any other Japanese cultivars. Previous work on geographical analysis for heading traits revealed that the